

FORMULATION OF LANSOPRAZOLE FOAM TABLETS: A NOVEL APPROACH TO ENHANCED GASTROINTESTINAL THERAPY**Parthiban S.¹, Anupama H. B.^{2*}, Chiranth Gowda B. C.³, Yashaswini N. R.⁴**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to formulate controlled-release foam tablets of Lansoprazole using hydrophobic polymeric matrices comprising Ethyl Cellulose (EC), Eudragit S, and Polyvinyl Pyrrolidone (PVP). Preformulation studies confirmed drug identity and purity through melting point analysis (192–195.1°C) and UV spectroscopy (λ_{max} at 281 nm). FTIR analysis showed no significant drug–excipient interactions, indicating chemical compatibility. Twelve formulations (F1–F12) were prepared and evaluated for precompression and post-compression parameters. All batches exhibited excellent flow properties, acceptable hardness (6.41–7.47 kg/cm²), low friability (<1%), and uniform drug content (88.45–92.26%) within pharmacopeial standards. *In-vitro* drug release studies showed sustained release over 8 hours, with cumulative release ranging from 87% to 91.5%. Formulations with lower EC and

higher PVP concentrations demonstrated faster release, while increased Eudragit S content contributed to improved early-phase control. Drug release followed Zero-order kinetics and fit well with the Korsmeyer–Peppas model ($n > 1$), indicating a Super Case II transport mechanism involving diffusion, swelling, and erosion. Among all, formulation F3 showed the most favourable release profile. The study concludes that appropriate polymer ratios can effectively modulate Lansoprazole release, supporting the development of a stable, gastro-resistant controlled-release dosage form.

KEYWORDS: Lansoprazole, Controlled release, Foam tablets, Super Case II transport, Zero-

order kinetics.

INTRODUCTION^[1-3]

Peptic ulcer disease is a gastrointestinal disorder characterized by mucosal damage due to gastric acid and pepsin secretion. It commonly occurs in the stomach and duodenum, with major causes being *Helicobacter pylori* infection and long-term use of NSAIDs. Current management relies on proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), which effectively suppress gastric acid secretion and promote healing. PPIs, such as omeprazole, pantoprazole, and lansoprazole, act by irreversibly inhibiting the gastric H⁺/K⁺-ATPase pump, thereby reducing acid secretion. However, conventional formulations of PPIs face challenges such as poor stability, degradation in acidic pH, and reduced bioavailability. To overcome these limitations, novel drug delivery systems are being explored.

Oral drug delivery remains the most preferred route due to convenience and patient compliance, but conventional tablets often fail to maintain prolonged gastric residence, reducing therapeutic efficacy. Gastro-retentive and modified-release systems offer better control over drug release, enhanced absorption, and improved therapeutic action.

Among innovative approaches, oral foam tablets (OFTs) have emerged as promising dosage forms. They combine effervescence and foam formation to enhance drug dispersion, stability, and bioavailability. Their porous structure allows controlled release, improved floatability, and ease of swallowing, making them especially suitable for pediatric and geriatric patients. Additionally, OFTs can protect moisture-sensitive drugs such as lansoprazole, ensuring stability and therapeutic efficiency.

Thus, the development of oral foam tablets represents a novel strategy to improve stability, absorption, and patient compliance in the treatment of peptic ulcer disease using PPIs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pure drug Lansoprazole and all excipients Ethyl cellulose, Eudragit-S, lactose, HPMC, PVP, SLS, magnesium stearate, and talc were of analytical/pharma grade and procured from standard suppliers.

Preformulation Studies^[4-5]

The drug was characterized for melting point (capillary method), λ_{\max} in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (UV scan 200–400 nm), and calibration curve (5–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ at 281 nm). Drug–

excipient compatibility was assessed using FTIR spectra ($4000\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of pure drug and physical mixtures with polymers.

Formulation of Lansoprazole Oral Foam Tablets^[6]

Tablets were prepared by wet granulation. Drug, polymers, and excipients were blended, granulated with binder, dried, sieved, and compressed into tablets.

Table 1: Formulation code for Oral Foam Tablet.

Sl. No	INGREDI ENTS	F1(mg)	F29 (mg)	F39 (mg)	F4 (mg)	F5 (mg)	F6 (mg)	F7 (mg)	F8 (mg)	F9 (mg)	F10 (mg)	F11 (mg)	F12 (mg)
1	Lansoprazole	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
2	Ethyl cellulose	15	60	15	30	30	60	30	60	60	30	15	15
3	Eudragit-S	45	15	15	45	15	15	45	45	45	15	45	15
4	Lactose	75.6	60.6	105.6	57	87	57	60.6	27	30.6	90.6	72	102
5	HPMC	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2
6	Magnesium Stearate	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
7	Talc	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
8	Polyvinyl pyrrolidone	1.8	1.8	1.8	5.4	5.4	5.4	1.8	5.4	1.8	1.8	5.4	5.4
9	Sodium lauryl sulfate	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8

Evaluation of Pre-compression Parameters^[7-10]

Evaluated different flow properties of powder like Bulk and tapped density, Angle of repose, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index.

Evaluation of tablet^[11-14]

Determined Weight Variation, Friability, Hardness, Thickness.

Determination of Drug Content uniformity

The tablets were tested for their drug content uniformity. At random 20 tablets were weighed and powdered. The powder equivalent to 180 was weighed accurately and dissolved in 100ml of Phosphate buffer pH 6.8. Then 1ml of this solution was transfer to the 10 ml volumetric flask and final volume was made by same solutions. Finally, absorbance of prepared solution was measured at 281nm using UV Visible spectrophotometer. The percentage drug content was calculated.

In-vitro dissolution studies

In vitro release studies of Lansoprazole from all formulations were performed according to USP type II, paddle method. Paddle speed was maintained at 50 rpm and 900ml of Phosphate buffers pH 6.8 was used as the dissolution medium. Samples were collected at

predetermined time intervals and replaced with equal volume of fresh medium, filtered through a Whatman filter paper, and analysed with a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at λ_{max} 281 nm. Drug concentration was calculated from a standard calibration plot and expressed as cumulative % drug dissolved. The release studies were performed in replicates of 3.

Drug Release Kinetics Stability Studies

The optimized formulation was subjected to intermediate stability testing as per ICH guidelines ($30^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ / $65\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$) for 90 days and evaluated for physical appearance, drug content, and dissolution profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies confirmed the identity and purity of Lansoprazole, with melting point and DSC values matching pharmacopoeial standards. UV spectroscopic analysis showed a λ_{max} at 281 nm, and calibration plots exhibited excellent linearity ($r^2 = 0.999$), validating the method for quantitative estimation. FTIR spectra of Lansoprazole and physical mixtures with Ethyl Cellulose and Eudragit S showed retention of characteristic absorption bands, indicating no significant drug–excipient interactions. These findings established the suitability of selected excipients for formulation development.

The precompression parameters of powder blends, including bulk and tapped density, angle of repose, Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio, were within pharmacopoeial limits, demonstrating good flow and compressibility. This ensured smooth granulation and compression processes. Post-compression evaluation confirmed that all tablet formulations met standard requirements for hardness, friability, thickness, and weight variation. Drug content uniformity (88–92%) indicated homogeneous distribution of the drug across all batches.

In vitro dissolution studies demonstrated that all formulations provided sustained release of Lansoprazole over 8 hours, with cumulative release ranging between 88–92%. Among these, F3 and F10 exhibited optimized release profiles, balancing polymer concentration and matrix integrity to achieve prolonged and consistent drug delivery.

The release kinetics analysis revealed that the dissolution data fitted best to the zero- order model (r^2 up to 0.998), indicating concentration-independent release. Korsmeyer–Peppas analysis further confirmed a super case-II transport mechanism ($n > 1$), suggesting that

polymer relaxation and erosion contributed significantly to drug release. In contrast, first-order and Higuchi models showed weaker correlations, reinforcing that controlled release followed zero-order kinetics. These results highlight the efficiency of the polymeric matrix system in modulating drug release.

Intermediate stability testing for 90 days under ICH conditions (30°C/65% RH) showed minimal reduction in drug content (92.26% to 91.02%) and cumulative release (91.59% to 89.24%), with no observable physical changes. This confirms that the optimized formulations maintained chemical stability and release performance over the study period.

Overall, Lansoprazole oral foam tablets prepared by wet granulation demonstrated satisfactory physicochemical properties, stability, and controlled release behaviour. The optimized formulations, particularly F3 and F10, provided sustained drug release with zero-order kinetics, offering a promising approach to improve therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance in the oral delivery of Lansoprazole.

Fig. 1: DSC graph of pure Lansoprazole.

Fig. 2: FTIR spectra of pure drug.

Fig. 3: FTIR spectra of Physical mixture.

Fig. 4: Hardness of Oral Foam Tablet.

Fig. 5: Thickness of Oral Foam Tablet.

Fig. 6: Friability of Oral Foam Tablet.

Fig. 7: Weight Variation of Oral Foam Tablet.

Fig. 8: Drug content uniformity of Oral Foam Tablet.

Fig. 9: *In vitro* drug release profile of F1-F12 formulation Table 6: Intermediate stability studies.

Parameter	Duration in days ($30^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} / 65\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$)		
	0	45	90
%DC	92.26	91.87	91.02
%CDR	91.59	91.05	89.24

CONCLUSION

Lansoprazole oral foam tablet was successfully prepared and evaluated. All twelve formulations showed excellent flow properties, compressibility, and uniformity suitable for tablet compression. Post-compression results met pharmacopeial standards with consistent hardness, friability, weight variation, and drug content (88–92%). Tablets achieved over 85% sustained release within 8 hours, following zero-order kinetics with polymer-controlled Super Case II transport. Stability studies demonstrated consistent drug content and release for 90 days, confirming the oral foam tablets as stable and suitable for further development.

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